

Wet extractors: crafting manual v1.2

Materials (see figures):

- Plastic funnels, \varnothing 10-15 cm, steep slope (at least 10 cm height)
- Rubber/silicone hoses, ca. 5 cm in length, tightly pushed up on the lower narrow part of the funnel
- Removable plugs for the bottom part of the hoses (i.e. clamp, squeeze clip). *Optional, can be replaced by tweezers/own fingers*
- Plastic/stainless steel kitchen sieves that fit snugly in the funnel (mesh 1-2 mm)
- Funnel holder – a device to keep the funnels upright, e.g., a board with holes
- Heat source on top of each funnel or a group of adjacent funnels (e.g. heating halogen or incandescent lamps ~60 Watts*)

Instructions: no manual is available; the pictures and elements are given below.

Photo credits: Rüdiger Schmelz

*The bulb may be surrounded by a hood to make the heat impact more efficient. For enchytraeid extraction it is important that the heat goes down to the bottom of the sieve, it should reach 40°C in the sample.